

Council for
BRITISH ARCHAEOLOGY
8 St. Andrew's Place, London, NW1 4LB

OI-486 1527

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Hon. Secretary: MR. P. J. FOWLER, M.A., F.S.A.

Secretary: MISS B. DE CARDI, F.S.A.

CONFIDENTIAL

8th October, 1972

Dear Andrew,

I wondered whether you would be attending David Stronach's paper next Monday, 13th October, to the B.I. P.S. If so, perhaps you could let me know if it would be possible to meet either here in the early afternoon or late morning, or alternatively after the paper?

I have twofold plans for work in the Lower Gulf during the winter of 1973/74. I had originally intended to undertake a fairly limited survey in the Ibri area in the hope of extending the distribution of the Umm an-Nar culture and excavating either a settlement or burial mound. I'm anxious, in the absence of full publication by the Danes, to see to what extent that culture tallies with the material at Bampur and Yahya, or whether the linked grey wares are just trade goods. The survey would obviously take account of all kinds of antiquities but my primary interest is Umm an-Nar. I shall also have a shot at getting myself up onto Jabal Akhdar to see what is there. Ibri is a possible base because Durham University will be working there and will have broken the local ice.

In addition to Oman, I have just been asked to put forward a programme for a comprehensive survey of antiquities on Qatar. The Qatar government is anxious to have a museum and is suddenly acutely conscious that there is an embarrassing gap between its Stone Age and the 19th century A.D. It is asking for instant archaeology with a survey to show exactly what it has - apparently the Danes after seven years work have only produced the report on the Stone Age material, though five burial cairns were excavated.

I am not able to undertake the survey until mid-October, 1973, and it would therefore be necessary to arrange for a short recce in the spring to pave the way for the main Expedition. I wondered whether you might be interested and able to join my team? Qatar is prepared to meet all expenses, provide accommodation, transport, and possibly a fee. For Oman, I would have to raise funds but half the battle would be won if I could take with me several persons from Qatar.

Knowing your interests in the Gulf I thought you might find the Qatar proposal in particular could be useful. If you were free to go out in the spring for four weeks in addition to joining me there in October I'd welcome your collaboration.

Even if your commitments tie you securely to the U.K. it would be useful to discuss the project if you can spare time. I'm anxious to collect a team with knowledge of the Iranian side, the one proviso being that they are British subjects. You are probably in closer touch with likely persons than I am and may even know what they are like both professionally as well as personally.

My proposals have to be outlined and submitted to the Qatar representatives within 2-3 weeks so perhaps you'd let me have a reply fairly soon. Meanwhile, please regard my plans as confidential.

In haste,

Yours sincerely,

Bernice de Zard

Andrew Williamson, Esq.,
15 St. John's Street,
Oxford.

PROPOSALS AND REQUIREMENTS FOR A SURVEY OF ANTIQUITIES IN QATAR

put forward by Beatrice de Cardi, B.A., F.S.A

1. SCOPE OF THE SURVEY

Qatar's claim to archaeological fame at present rests largely on its Stone Age sites which are more richly represented there than in any other part of Arabia. About 200 are already known but more undoubtedly await discovery. They range from sites where flint implements were made to the potentially more informative encampments of their users -- hunter/fishermen living for the most part on the cliffs along the south-western and north-eastern coasts near Dukhan and Khor respectively. Little is known about the way of life of these people but a study of their implements suggests that hunter/fisher groups roamed the Qatar peninsula from the Middle Stone Age to the Early Neolithic, a period of vital interest which saw the introduction of animal and plant domestication and the formation of small settlements in other Gulf countries. The Qatar artifacts can be divided into three or four distinct cultural groups covering a wide and at present imprecise time range currently thought to be between twenty to forty thousand years ago.

This wealth of Stone Age material is of great importance in the archaeology of Qatar since it could provide the basic structure for the Stone Age of Arabia. It is a subject deserving further study which could, with imaginative treatment, provide Qatar Museum with a section of not only local, but international interest and importance.

The implements recovered from known sites have already been studied typologically but the scientific examination of selected working and camping sites of the different cultural groups might throw new light on their environmental background. This approach is one which is being used increasingly to reconstruct the wider picture of early man against a particular landscape and the method could produce significant results in Qatar. To this end the survey team would include both a specialist in Stone Age studies and a Geomorphologist.

An objective of the survey would be the location of a settlement site providing evidence of occupation in the form of hearths, stains, hollows or other man-made features on the land surface. Such a site, if recorded in detail, could be 'lifted' and reconstructed within the Museum. Supported by appropriate visual material and with implements displayed imaginatively to illustrate their use, an exhibit of this kind could have considerable popular appeal. At the same

An objective of the survey would be the location of a settlement site providing evidence of occupation in the form of hearths, stains, hollows or other man-made features on the land surface. Such a site, if recorded in detail, could be 'lifted' and reconstructed within the Museum. Supported by appropriate visual material and with implements displayed imaginatively to illustrate their use, an exhibit of this kind could have considerable popular appeal. At the same time provision should be made for a study collection commensurate with the importance of the Stone Age material to international scholars.

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Other ancient sites of particular interest in Qatar are burial cairns and mounds. Many different types are known from adjacent countries where they range in date from the third to the first millennium B.C. but few have been scientifically excavated. As yet the Qatar cairns have not provided datable pottery and all that can be said of their builders is that they lived "in the days of ignorance". A member of the survey team, experienced in the excavation of similar sites, would make a detailed survey seeking evidence of occupation near the cairns and would note any structural differences in the monuments. Should cairns of varying types be found, one of each kind would be excavated in the hope that grave-goods would enable the different structures to be dated.

Even if, as so often happens, the cairns proved to have been robbed in antiquity, a detailed study of their plans, etc., would be of value in relating them to comparable structures in other parts of Arabia and thereby helping to date them. As a familiar feature of the landscape, the reconstruction of a cairn or a mound to reveal the details of the underlying burial might be a feature of popular interest to those visiting the Museum. This could be either in the form of a scale model or an actual reconstruction in the Museum compound if space allowed.

A major aspect of the survey would be the search for new evidence on which to build the over-all framework of Qatar's history since the Stone Age. The recent discovery of pottery in Dharan and Buraimi related to the Ubaid and Jemdet Nasr periods in Mesopotamia (5th-4th millennium) suggests that Qatar might yield similar material. An ancient east-west trade route running south of the peninsula is thought to have been used until dunes covered it during the first millennium A.D. Search among the barkans in that area might not only reveal fourth millennium or earlier sites but might also throw light on trade with Gerrha during the Seleucid period. So far the only Seleucid site recorded in Qatar is that at Ras Uwainat Ali but other settlements may have existed in the south and along the western and northern coasts.

It would also be reasonable to look for evidence of contact with the Dilmun culture of Bahrain (3rd millennium) along those shores and to see whether coves on the north-eastern coast were used by merchants trading between Mesopotamia and the Indus valley at that time.

The northern coast might also reflect trading activities down the Gulf in later periods. Situated almost opposite Siraf, a Sasanian port which became the main entrepot for goods from the Far East during the 9th century A.D., some degree of commercial contact is likely to have existed. The inclusion in the survey team of an archaeologist currently engaged in research on early Islamic sites would ensure that due attention was given to sites of this period. He also plans to examine post-Hellenistic settlement with particular emphasis on the importance of the pearling industry and the trade of the Gulf with India, in which Qatari merchants were involved from at least a century before the Hejira. There is evidence from elsewhere in the Gulf that the origins of large-scale pearling c.300 B.C. were based on techniques by which oysters were opened on dry land, leaving clear archaeological remains. An examination of such remains could reveal the role that Qatar, lying so close to the main Gulf beds, played in this development. It is therefore requested (below, Para.6b) that a sample of the shells recovered by made available in the U.K. for technical comparison with modern species.

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Nor would evidence of the Portuguese period be neglected. Sixteenth-century maps refer to a city in Qatar and indicate a fort. Towns such as Al-Zubara and other coastal sites would be visited since a study of surface sherds might prove informative, particularly in showing the amount and range of Chinese porcelain and Far Eastern wares which were imported into Qatar during the 16th-17th centuries.

4. DURATION OF THE SURVEY

It is suggested that the Director should visit Qatar early in 1973 to discuss the Survey and outline the facilities required. If the Danish archaeologist, Hølgar Kapel, was in Qatar, it would be most useful to meet him and to visit some Stone Age sites in his company. A brief visit would also be made to areas of special archaeological interest in order to decide upon the location of the Expedition's headquarters and area camps (see Para.9c, Accommodation).

The full survey would be carried out during the winter of 1973 when the team would spend at least ten weeks in Qatar (8 weeks in the field; 2 weeks in camp preparing records and material for transfer to the Qatar Government). The Survey could, if required, be extended by a further couple of weeks.

It is suggested that the team should arrive during the latter part of October, 1973, and leave either at the end of December or in mid January, 1974. Guidance in the choice of dates for arrival and departure would be appreciated so that Ramadhan and major public holidays might be avoided.

5. CONSERVATION

The present proposals only cover field survey supported by the excavation of a few selected sites (see Paras. 1-2). No provision has been made for the study of epigraphical material or the preparation of casts from rock-carvings, of which many interesting groups exist. Nor would the survey team include a specialist to undertake the conservation of finds resulting from excavations. It is assumed that when a Museum is established technically qualified staff would be appointed or a technician sent for training to an appropriate centre such as the Laboratory of the University of London Institute of Archaeology which provides a three-year course.

6. DISPOSAL OF FINDS

With regard to the pottery, flint implements and other material resulting from the Survey, it is assumed that these would be required to form the nucleus of the new Museum collections. It is however hoped that consideration might be given to the following points:-

- (a) that a small but fully representative study collection would be made available by the Qatar Government to an appropriate museum or institute in the U.K. to stimulate research in Eastern Arabian and Gulf archaeology;
- (b) that permission would be given for the export of soil and other samples requiring scientific analysis in a laboratory in the U.K., together with shells for comparison with modern species.
- (c) that in the case of important material requiring detailed comparative study of a kind impossible to undertake in Qatar, permission would be given for its export to the U.K. for a limited period of time. All the material so exported would be returned to Qatar after study at the end of the specified period.

7. RECORDS

Upon the conclusion of the Survey a complete list of sites and finds located during the Survey would be submitted to the Qatar Government.

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8. PUBLICATION It is suggested that discussion of the forms which publication might take should be deferred until the results of the Survey are known. In the event of a Museum being established in Qatar there would be obvious advantages in presenting the information as two separate publications. One, intended for the specialist reader and international scholar, should take the form of a well-illustrated monograph comprising detailed papers by the specialists responsible for the excavations and area surveys carried out. To this might be added an introductory paper by an eminent archaeologist, together with other reports on material or aspects of research not directly covered by the survey team. The Director would be responsible for collating and editing this monograph for publication by the Qatar Government.

The monograph might serve as the basis for a second publication - a popular Guide to Qatar's Antiquities - prepared by the Ministry of Information and printed in both Arabic and English. The cost of this publication could be recouped from sales in the Museum.

QATAR ARCHAEOLOGICAL EXPEDITION

His Highness the Emir has now approved proposals and given his support to the Expedition. The project has been discussed in detail with the Director of the Ministry of Information and it will be necessary to provide him with a detailed schedule indicating as fully as possible what the Expedition will do from the time of its arrival in Qatar. This schedule has to be provided by mid-April and your collaboration is needed if satisfactory provision is to be made for the work you intend to undertake.

Brief notes on the points discussed with the Government of Qatar are given below together with general information about conditions, &c.

DATE & DURATION

In order to avoid Ramadhan and the subsequent Id al-Fitr, departure has been deferred from the date (27th October) originally envisaged. The Director and Interpreter will leave for Doha shortly after 1st November and the rest of the team will follow approximately one week later. Precise dates cannot be given until the winter flight schedules are known but you should be available to leave during the period 8-14th November, 1973, and to remain in Qatar for about ten weeks or as long as arranged individually.

DISPOSAL OF FINDS

All flint implements, pottery and other objects found during survey and excavation are the property of the Qatar Government and will be handed over on conclusion of the excavations. Team members are asked particularly to respect this ruling: strict antiquities legislation is being drafted and the unauthorised export of archaeological material could prejudice other archaeological expeditions in the future.

Upon the conclusion of the Expedition's work the Qatar Government will consider whether a small study collection (flints and potsherds) may be exported to the U.K. for deposit in a museum or teaching institution. Permission to export soil and other samples, and the short-term loan of any material requiring study for comparative purposes in U.K. would be considered at the same time.

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Essential plans and drawings and other records would be photocopied by the Government of Qatar, one set being kept there, the other being given to the Expedition which would retain the original site books from which the records had been prepared. An index of sites would be prepared for the Ministry of Information, but punch cards made to facilitate the Expedition's work would not be required.

PHOTOGRAPHS

All photographs, both monochrome and colour must be scrutinised by the Ministry of Information before the Expedition leaves the country. The main photographic record will be made in monochrome and the Expedition would be provided with such prints as were needed for record purposes and for publication. Colour transparencies taken for personal use by members of the Expedition should be on Ektachrome not Kodachrome film since processing facilities exist locally only for the former. It takes 30-35 days to send and get back Kodachrome and there is risk of losing the film en route in the post. Copies of colour transparencies may be required by the Ministry of Information.

BASE CAMP

Preliminary survey showed an overwhelming density of sites along the west coast. For that reason Dukhan will be used as base if accommodation can be provided by Qatar Petroleum Co. It is hoped that a house will be available and that team members may use the canteen and the supermarket - there are no other shops in Dukhan. At least four weeks could usefully be spent there by all members as there are burial mounds on Ras Abaruk ($\frac{3}{4}$ hr. away); Seleucid sherds and a possible structure at Ras Uwainat Ali ($\frac{1}{2}$ hr. away); and Palaeolithic and Neolithic sites have existed on the plateau and the shore - though the surface implements have been removed and these sites are now difficult to locate. The Expedition would spend the last fortnight in Dukhan preparing the preliminary report to be handed over to the Ministry of Information before departure.

AREA CAMPS

It is probably that the Expedition will split up after four weeks in order that survey and excavation can be undertaken in other areas beyond the daily reach of Dukhan. The Director will require to know well in advance the areas in which teams will be operating in order to make the necessary arrangements. Trailer accommodation, with cooking facilities, will be provided but work camps for labourers and water require prior arrangement.

Both in base and area camps sleeping accommodation will have to be shared.

VEHICLES & DRIVERS

Two four-wheel drive vehicles will be provided, each with a driver who will be responsible for the car. Foreign visitors to Qatar have to take a driving test before a local license is issued, and English driving licenses should be taken with you. Sabkha (particularly after rain) is a special hazard and the responsibility for the vehicles must rest firmly with the Government-provided drivers.

INSURANCE

Team members are advised to consider what arrangements they wish to make to cover accidents, thefts and loss of baggage. Medical expenses are less likely to be heavy in Qatar than elsewhere since the Government provides a free medical and hospital service to all comers. The Archaeology Abroad Service has made arrangements with Lloyds Underwriters to provide insurance at economical premiums and inquiries might be made from the Secretary, A.A.S., 31-34 Gordon Square, London WC1H 0PY, and from other sources. The Ministry of Information will arrange insurance for the vehicles but the labourers are not covered - though compensation may be paid for injury.

ENTRY REGULATIONS

Entry visas are not required by holders of U.K. passports endorsed "British subject: Citizen of the UK and Colonies". Residence permits are usually needed after one month but this would be arranged by the Ministry of Information. Holders of passports issued outside the U.K should check with the Embassy of Qatar, 10 Reeves Mews, London, W.1, if in doubt about the regulations.

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HEALTH REGULATIONS

Entry is subject to holding valid certificates of vaccination against smallpox and cholera. If you have had these recently, please check that they will remain valid throughout your stay - cholera holds good for only six months. Those arriving from a country where yellow fever is endemic or epidemic will require a certificate of inoculation. TAB (against typhoid, paratyphoid, etc) is optional, but discuss this with your doctor.

Free vaccination and inoculations can be obtained at the Hospital for Tropical Diseases, 4 St. Pancras Way, NW1. If more than smallpox and cholera are required, check on the order in which they should be done. Work out roughly when you want to have your jabs and arrange appointments with the Hospital well in advance as they sometimes have long waiting lists. Private doctors usually charge for cholera, etc. as not being on the National Health.

Qatar is virtually free of epidemic diseases but newcomers get mild enteritis and prickly head so come armed to deal with both. Have a dental check up before departure. Sun-glasses are essential to counter the glare from sand: they are cheaper to buy in UK but obtainable in Doha if required. Sandstorms are to be expected so bring what you need if prone to eye complaints.

FAUNA

Kraits - a small, aggressive and deadly snake is said to reside in the Dukhan area and they usually like the looser soil to be found in burials and in the bottom of trenches. Be wary and also watch out for scorpions large and small both in the house and on the side of trenches. Flies are a nuisance and materialise from nowhere.

CLIMATE

November temperature: max. 34.6; min. 13.5
December temperature: max. 27.6; min. 08.0

Humidity is about 70% so bring cotton clothing in preference to non-absorbent man-made fibres. A dusting powder (Johnson's Baby) is useful to prevent prickly heat. Nights will be cold; and even in the day there can be variations in temperature according to whether the wind blows from the sea or off the desert. Clothing that can be piled on or peeled off to suit conditions is essential.

Some rain can be expected during the winter and since there is little vegetation run off accumulates rapidly in any depression; a point to be borne in mind when camping or selecting a site for excavation.

CLOTHING

In addition to the points mentioned under Climate, the following may be helpful.

Desert boots reaching over the ankle give some protection against snakes. They can be bought (Czech made) in the Doha market but are rather stiff: price about £2.40-£2.75. On no account pad about without shoes either indoors or outside. Shorts and working without a short are unacceptable, the Qataris being Sunni Muslims of the Wahabi sect. Swimming is possible in Dukhan within an enclosure - shared with sea-snakes. Shirts, jeans (tapered legs), caps available in Doha market. Qatar is informal by Gulf standards but one respectable suit is needed. It would be best to bring it in a polythene cover. It is possible to have a suit made in Doha in a week: light weight cost about £17-£25; UK worsteds cost more.

AVAILABILITY OF SUPPLIES

Most toilet goods are available in Doha but cost more than in U.K. Aim to bring what you need from U.K. with the exception of cigarettes. These are cheaper in Doha than on the plane: 200 Dunhill filter-tip cost QR.10 (a little over £1). No alcohol can be imported or bought. If you have a lightweight Hounsfield camp bed it would be as well to bring it: camp beds are heavy and expensive. Also bring a light sleeping bag if you have one; otherwise make do with a kapok-filled quilt from the market where pillows are available.

CURRENCY

The Qatar riyal was recently introduced but Qatar/Dubai riyals are still accepted. In March, 1973, the official rate was £1=QR9.40 but moneychangers in the market gave QR 9.75 for a pound note so its worth taking the maximum £25 in cash. If you take Traveller's Cheques consult your Bank nearer the time as to whether Sterling or Dollar cheques are best. The rate for £1 was QR 3.80 (official), QR 3.85 (unofficial).

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QR notes are issued in the following denominations:- 1, 5, 10, 25, 50, 100; coins, 1, 5, 10, 25 and 50 dirhams, 100 dirhams = QR1.

POSTAL SERVICES

departure.

Air letters to UK take 3-4 days. A forwarding address will be notified nearer the time of

OFFICE HOURS

Banks: 8-11.30, Saturdays - Thursdays, closed Fridays.
Govt. offices: 6-1 do.
Commercial: 8-noon, 4-6 p.m.do.
Oil company: 7-noon, 1-3 or 4 p.m. Sat-Wed.
Embassy: 8-1.30, Sat-Thurs.
Shops: as commercial, but some open on Friday in the market for a few hours in the morning.

These vary so if you have a number of calls to make you have to plan your visits carefully.

TAXIS

Identified by yellow number plates. No meters so agree the fare before getting in.

LECTURES

the Expedition to give a lecture on an appropriate topic. Please notify me so that I can arrange nearer the time.

The British Council opened an office in Doha six months ago and has invited any member of

FEES

H.H. the Emir has agreed to the payment of a fee to members of the Expedition, varying on the time spent in Qatar. The fee would be payable on the conclusion of the Expedition's work. Those staying for the duration could expect £150.

9.

FACILITIES REQUIRED

(a) Preliminary visit (Para.4) The Director would require accommodation and transport during her visit which should be arranged at a time when officials of the Ministry of Information would be available for discussion. If Hølger Kapel should be in Qatar, the Director would like to consult him so that advantage can be taken of his knowledge and experience in locating Stone Age sites. Transport would be needed to visit those areas where the density of sites is greatest.

(b) Pre-Survey requirements Field survey has to be preceded by a detailed study of air-photographs and maps, combined with an examination of the documentary sources. In order that this preliminary research may start as soon as the project has been approved, it would be necessary for a complete set of air-photographs to be made available in London, with authorisation for their use. It is understood that a new series of maps should be available in the spring, 1973, and it is requested that six sets of maps should be provided at the earliest opportunity so that each member of the team engaged on survey may plan his research as far in advance as possible.

(c) Requirements in the field In order that two small survey teams may operate simultaneously in different parts of the peninsula careful consideration will have to be given to Accommodation and Transport.

Accommodation A headquarters camp capable of accommodating not more than six persons at any one time would be required. This should consist of sleeping quarters, dining-room, large workroom with adequate table and storage space (shelving) and if possible electricity. A kitchen, equipped with gas stove and refrigerator, crockery, cutlery, etc., would be needed with quarters for a Cook and one servant. An adequate water supply is essential.

The location of this headquarters might be near Dukhan a headquarters in that area would have obvious advantages. In addition, the use of short-term camps for small survey teams would be needed in other parts. It is suggested that the Qatar Government might indicate where such accommodation could most easily be provided; area surveys might then be based on such centres.

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The location of this headquarters might be discussed during the Director's preliminary visit. Since many sites lie near Dukhan a headquarters in that area would have obvious advantages. In addition, the use of short-term camps for small survey teams would be needed in other parts. It is suggested that the Qatar Government might indicate where such accommodation could most easily be provided; area surveys might then be based on such centres.

Transport

The limited use of a helicopter at the outset of the Survey would be extremely useful as a means of checking sites noted on air-photographs.

The field survey would require the full-time use of two Landrovers, with permission to use an additional vehicle should labour and equipment have to be transported on occasion between sites.

Limited use would also be made of a small motorised boat for coastal survey on probably a few days by the Geomorphologist and by the specialist working on the pearling industry. It is assumed that suitable craft could be hired when required.

Animal transport might be needed for survey in dune areas, subject to local advice. Since the survey team will include persons able to drive Landrovers it would not be necessary for the two vehicles to be accompanied by two drivers: one driver would suffice.

COMPOSITION AND DUTIES
OF THE SURVEY TEAM

The team would be kept to a minimum, members being chosen for their ability and qualifications to perform the objectives of the Survey. Each member - apart from the Camp Organiser - would be expected to prepare a detailed report on his subject for publication in the monograph. The team would be as follows:-

DIRECTOR

Responsible for the over-all planning and coordination of the Survey, both in advance and in the field. She would undertake the selection and briefing of the team, and would visit Qatar early in 1973 to make the preliminary arrangements. During the Survey, she would select sites for excavation and would carry out area surveys, preparing the results for publication. She would supervise the recording of finds and sites, and would initiate a punch-card index to facilitate information retrieval both in the field and in the Museum. She would compile the final list of sites located and would collate and edit the monograph for publication (Para.8).

ASSISTANT

Responsible for collecting documentary information before the Survey and presenting it in the monograph. He would undertake area survey and make a special study of the pearling industry (Para.3), preparing the results for publication. He would assist in the comparative study of first millennium A.D. and later material. The Assistant would arrive in Qatar during the third week of the Survey.

SPECIALIST IN STONE
AGE STUDIES

to study the Stone Age assemblages of Qatar in relation to adjacent countries. He would excavate sites selected in consultation with the Director and the Geomorphologist and would report on the results. He would consider the requirements of Qatar Museum when packaging the Stone Age finds by noting those assemblages most worthy of display and by indicating the nature of the individual artifacts, where possible. He would select and supervise the drawing of the implements for publication.

GEOMORPHOLOGIST

to spend three weeks with the survey team, working in close collaboration with the Stone Age specialist. He would try to establish a chronology for changes in the landscape and climate. He would return to the U.K. on the arrival of the Assistant.

SITE SUPERVISOR

to carry out a survey of cairns and pre-Islamic burial mounds with the Director and

GEOMORPHOLOGIST

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SITE SUPERVISOR

to carry out a survey of cairns and pre-Islamic burial mounds with the Director and to excavate selected sites, preparing reports on their structure, finds, etc., for publication. He would be responsible for training the small labour force required for this work.

SURVEYOR/DRAUGHTSMAN

to collaborate in the area surveys and prepare maps, plans and sections needed for the monograph.

CAMP ORGANISER

to organise the base and area camps, commissariat and payment of labour. He would supervise the regular maintenance of the vehicles. An important aspect of his duties would be to act as Interpreter (Arabic and Urdu) in order to make known the purpose of the survey and collect relevant information about potential sites from local sources. He would help in the training of the local labour force.

11.

LOCAL LABOUR

Requirements are as follows:-

1 Cook (a Pakistani with experience of English cooking)

1 Servant

1 Landrover Driver

20 Labourers (recruited near the sites to be excavated)

Nightwatchman and Guides. Advice would be sought as to the need for these.

OTHER LOCAL HELPERS

The services of a professional photographer might be required occasionally. Amateur archaeologists willing to help in sorting and registering finds, and persons able to draw flints under supervision would be welcomed.

QUALIFICATIONS AND EXPERIENCE OF THE SURVEY TEAMDIRECTOR

B. de Z

Has been Secretary of the Council for British Archaeology since 1949. She has been engaged on research on the archaeology of the countries on both sides of the Lower Gulf for many years and has planned and directed field surveys and excavation as follows: 1948: survey in Kalat State, Pakistan Baluchistan; 1949: survey in Afghanistan; 1957: survey and excavations in Kalat, Pakistan Baluchistan (published by the Government of Pakistan in Pakistan Archaeology, 2 (1965), 86-182); 1966: survey and excavations in Persian Baluchistan (published as a monograph in the Anthropological Series of the American Museum of Natural History, New York, vol.51, pt.3 (1970), 233-355); 1968: survey in Ras al Khaimah and Fujairah, Trucial States (published in East & West, n.s.vol.21.3-4 (1971), 225-289); survey in the Musandam Peninsula, Northern Oman carried out during the winter of 1971-72 (note in forthcoming issue of Antiquity and report in preparation for publication in East & West).

A graduate of the University of London and a Fellow of the Society of Antiquaries of London; a Vice-President of the Royal Archaeological Institute.

ASSISTANT

A. G. W.

Currently Randall-MacIver Student in Archaeology (Junior Research Fellow) at Queens College, Oxford. At present engaged in an archaeological and historical study of Gulf trade from 200 B.C. to 1500 A.D. Has made a surface examination of sites in U.A.E., Ras al Khaima and elsewhere. Has studied the pottery from Eastern Saudi Arabia in western collections. Has taken part in survey and directed excavations at Sirjan and Dab'ud Deh, southern Iran, for three seasons. Is presenting a Doctoral thesis to the University of Oxford in 1973 on "The maritime cities of the Gulf and their commercial role from the 5th century A.D. to 1507". Publications in the Journal of the British Institute of Persian Studies; The Papers of the Peabody Museum, Harvard University. Is trained to take soil and C14 samples, can help with surveying and photography.

SPECIALIST IN STONE AGE STUDIES

G. H. Smith

Currently working on a doctoral thesis at the University of London, Institute of Archaeology, to be presented in 1973. Has collaborated in the excavation of Stone Age sites in India and will be working with Mr. R. Leakey on Palaeolithic sites in East Africa in the summer of 1973.

GEOMORPHOLOGIST

Dr. C. Vita-Finzi Currently Lecturer at University College,

SPECIALIST IN STONE AGE STUDIES *G.H. Smith*

collaborated in the excavation of Stone Age sites in India and will be working with Mr. R. Leakey on Palaeolithic sites in East Africa in the summer of 1973.

GEOMORPHOLOGIST *Dr. C. Vita-Finzi* Currently Lecturer at University College, London, working on Late Quaternary environmental changes in various parts of the Old World including Musandam, Northern Oman. Among the topics considered is that of earth movements, hence the importance of complementing the Oman work with data from other parts of the Gulf. Publications: The Mediterranean Valleys (Cambridge Univ. Press, 1969); Late Quaternary alluvial chronology of Iran, Geol. Rasch., 58 (1969), 951-973.

M.A., Ph.D. (Cantab.). Speaks a little Arabic, can take soil samples and has a knowledge of geology.

SITE SUPERVISOR *D.G. Buckley* Currently Research Assistant working with Inspectorate of Ancient Monuments, Department of the Environment. Present duties involve excavation, including cairn sites, and preparation of the material for publication. Graduate (B.Sc.) University of London. Can identify bones and advise on conservation in the field, draw plans, etc. and survey.

CAMP ORGANISER *G. Barrington* Was responsible for overland journeys from U.K. to Pakistan and Persian Baluchistan when the Director carried out surveys and excavations in 1957 and 1966. Speaks Arabic and Urdu; has attended training courses on mechanics of Landrovers; experience in organising Expedition camps.

ARCHAEOLOGICAL EXPEDITION TO CENTRAL OMAN, 1974

Proposals submitted by Miss Beatrice de Cardi, B.A., F.S.A., of the Council for British Archaeology, 8 St. Andrew's Place, Regent's Park, London, N.W.1

INTRODUCTION

In January, 1972, His Majesty Qabus Bin Said, Sultan of Oman, graciously allowed Miss de Cardi to undertake a survey of archaeological sites in the Musandam peninsula. A short article on a small Sasanian outpost discovered on Jazirat al-Ghanam has already appeared in Antiquity, vol. XLVI.184 (1972) (copy attached), and a full report on the survey is nearing completion and has been accepted for publication in East and West, a periodical with a wide international circulation issued in Rome. As an additional means of promoting interest in the archaeology of Oman, Miss de Cardi took advantage of the annual Seminar for Arabian Studies held in the University of London last year to report on the main results of her fieldwork.

The presence in Oman of several foreign missions during 1973 illustrates the growing importance attached to research in a country whose archaeological potential is still virtually untapped. Over the past decade fieldwork in neighbouring countries has gradually revealed links with the major civilisations which existed in southern Mesopotamia some four thousand years ago and evidence of a similar nature undoubtedly awaits discovery in central Oman.

APPLICATION

Miss de Cardi would welcome the opportunity of undertaking fieldwork in central Oman and would request that this application be submitted to His Majesty ~~The Sultan~~ for consideration. Subject to ~~His Majesty's~~ approval, permission is sought to carry out archaeological surveys, combined with selective excavation, in ~~the~~ regions: ~~IBRI and on JADAL AKHDAR~~. This work could be undertaken during a ten-week period starting in mid-January, 1974. Miss de Cardi would be accompanied by Mr. D.G. Buckley, B.Sc., currently Research Assistant in the Inspectorate of Ancient Monuments, Department of the Environment, and by Mr. G. Barrington, who would act as Interpreter. Permission is sought specifically for survey in ~~the two regions named; for the excavation of archaeological material to be deposited in a teaching institution or museum in the United Kingdom to stimulate the study of the archaeology of Oman.~~

regions. The work will be carried out over a week period starting in mid-January, 1974. Miss de Cardi would be accompanied by Mr. D.G. Buckley, B.Sc., currently Research Assistant in the Inspectorate of Ancient Monuments, Department of the Environment, and by Mr. G. Barrington, who would act as Interpreter. Permission is sought specifically for survey in the two regions named; for the excavation of selected prehistoric sites; and for the export of a small study collection of archaeological material to be deposited in a teaching institution or museum in the United Kingdom to stimulate interest in the archaeology of Oman.

FINANCE

No financial support would be required from the Government of Oman to implement this project. Miss de Cardi has been awarded a Churchill Fellowship to cover her expenses and Grants for the other members of the Expedition have been sought from the British Academy and the Society of Antiquaries of London.

PROPOSED RESEARCH

The purpose of this project is twofold:
(1) to provide limited help in recording antiquities in central Oman; and
(2) to obtain evidence of prehistoric settlement there and to relate it to the archaeology of adjacent countries.

(1) At a time when large-scale agricultural development, major roads and other projects necessary for the progress of the country could result in the destruction of archaeological sites without record, it is believed that the listing of antiquities even within two relatively restricted areas would serve a useful purpose and would extend knowledge of Oman's past. The surveys would be undertaken on a comprehensive basis, sites of all periods being recorded, and a card index giving their nature and location could, if required, be prepared for transfer to the appropriate Department. Fieldwork could, if the Government of Oman wished, be extended to include any areas in the vicinity of ~~Ibri and Jabal Akhdar~~ where development is likely to eradicate all trace of any antiquities which may exist.

(2) Ibri has been chosen as one of the areas for study since its position on an ancient caravan route suggests that evidence of early settlements and cairn-burials of prehistoric date might be found in that region. Two distinctive types of grey ware are known from burials in Abu Dhabi and similar wares occurred in a settlement excavated by Miss de Cardi in Persian Baluchistan. Since there was no close resemblance between the associated pottery on these sites, the grey wares may represent goods traded widely on both sides of the Gulf during the 3rd millennium. An examination of sites near Ibri might resolve this point since comparable wares are said to have been noted near cairns in the area and excavation of appropriate sites could prove informative. ~~On purely practical grounds, Ibri would be a particularly convenient base from which to operate initially because of the presence there of a team from Durham University which has signified its willingness to provide information about antiquities encountered in the course of its work.~~

~~Jabal Akhdar clearly poses difficulties of access which could only be surmounted with the active cooperation of the Oman Government.~~ Its inaccessibility, combined with an abundant water supply, must have made the mountain a sanctuary for pastoralists from early times and the region is of considerable interest to archaeologists for that reason. It is suggested that subject to ~~the~~ approval in principle to field-work on the mountain, Miss de Cardi would seek the advice of appropriate officials upon her arrival in Muscat and would plan her survey in the light of their experience and guidance.

PUBLICATION

Miss de Cardi would undertake to prepare an interim report on the completion of the survey and would ensure the publication of a full report in an appropriate periodical within a reasonable time.

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April, 1973